

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

HIGHER INCIDENCE OF MALARIA IN HIV-DISEASED PREGNANT WOMEN AND ITS IMPLICATIONS FOR MALARIA CONTROL

¹Dr Ahsan Nawaz, ²Dr Ambreen Shahid, ³Dr Zaynab Rashid

¹Jinnah Hospital Lahore

²Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi

³Medical Officer at Mohiudin Teaching Hospital Mirpur AJK

Article Received: September 2020 **Accepted:** October 2020 **Published:** November 2020

Abstract:

Aim: *Inspect pregnant women for the link between HIV disease and common intestinal diseases and decide, as for HIV disease, on the viability of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine to eliminate P. falciparum contamination.*

Methods: *Cross-sectional descriptive investigation of P. falciparum ubiquity in pregnant women at the beginning of the antenatal visit and in women during transport who had received two sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine drugs for jungle fever. HIV status was studied among 626 women who visited two provincial clinics in Lahore in 2019-20 for an antenatal visit and transport. Data were collected on maternal age, equality, and gestational age. The prevalence of P. falciparum was estimated at the start of the antenatal visit and transport. Our current research was conducted at Services Hospital Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. Women received two doses of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) as routine treatment at the first antenatal visit and between 28 and 34 weeks of development, thus adapting to the Government of Malawi's strategy on malaria control during pregnancy.*

Results: *Prevalence of HIV disease was 26.6% and all contaminations were HIV type-1. In prim gravidae Malariacommonness at enrollment was 57.4% in HIV-tainted and 37.6% in HIV-uninfected ladies (P 6 0.05). The corresponding figures for multigravidas were 24.9% and 14.2%, individually (P, 0.02). HIV-infected prim gravids had an increased prevalence of bowel disease at all ages of gestation. The predominance of the Pinnacle parasite occurred prior to the growth of HIV-infected promulgates (15-18 weeks if HIV-infected; 21-24 weeks if not HIV-infected). The general danger of parasitaemia in HIV-infected versus non-HIV-infected ladies was fundamentally increased in three of the five equality meetings, including the two most notable (equality .3), indicating that explicit resistance to intestinal disease was weakened. The prevalence of bowel disease during transport remained high among HIV-infected women, despite earlier daily practice of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine treatment during pregnancy. There was no critical contrast in the ubiquity of parasites at the time of transport between women who used and those who did not use sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine.*

Conclusion: *HIV infection is linked to a huge increase in the prevalence of Malariaamong pregnant women of all categories, the impact of which is evident from the beginning of incubation. Two sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine treatments have been lacking to release parasitaemia in many women during transport, regardless of HIV status and despite high susceptibility to MS. There is a need to attempt longitudinal surveys to determine the rate of P. falciparum infection in HIV-infected and non-HIV-infected pregnant women and to reconsider the recurrence and timing of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine therapy in these women. Re-dise of P. falciparum in late pregnancy probably clarifies the high ubiquity of the parasite at the time of transport after sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine treatment at 29 or 35 weeks of development.*

Keywords: *Higher Incidence, Malaria, HIV-Diseased Pregnant Women.*

Corresponding author:

Dr. Ahsan Nawaz,
Jinnah Hospital Lahore

Please cite this article in press Ahsan Nawaz et al, **Higher Incidence Of Malaria In HIV-Diseased Pregnant Women And Its Implications For Malaria Control**, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2020; 07(11).

INTRODUCTION:

In sub-Saharan nations endemic for Malaria practically 53% of all prim gravidae will be parasitemia from the outset antenatal visit. In a portion of these nations HIV sero positivity happens in upwards of one out of four unselected pregnant ladies [1]. The development of HIV in pregnant women infected with Malaria is a conceivable new circumstance for the control of Malaria during pregnancy, since there are no generally applied suggestions for the control of intestinal disease in pregnant women in Pakistan. Strategies vary from treatment with chloroquine and, in addition, week-by-week prophylaxis [2], irregular treatment with two servings of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine on a routine basis, suggestive treatment, screening followed by treatment of parasitized women, and routine pyrimethamine on a week-by-week basis. Similarly, approaches vary as to whether to focus only on prim gravidae, as they represent at most a serious danger of intestinal disease [3]. Multigravidas in holoendemic areas for intestinal disease create parity-specific invulnerability after recovery from parasitaemia in the first pregnancy. HIV disease weakens resistance, and an increased vulnerability to Malaria in higher equality gatherings may be normal. Increased vulnerability to Malaria has not been observed in HIV-infected children or pregnant adults, but there is evidence that this occurs in pregnant women [4]. The impact of HIV disease comparable to the effectiveness of drug control for bowel disease during pregnancy has not been studied. Given the great similarity of the two infections in sub-Saharan Pakistan and the likelihood that the current provisions for intestinal disease have a lesser effect in HIV-infected pregnant women, the magnitude of the impact of HIV infection on Malaria in pregnancy should be assessed with caution [5].

METHODOLOGY:

All women who visited emergency clinic prenatal offices were surveyed at their first visit after obtaining informed consent. The survey was completed by a prepared nurse who recalled data on age, previous use of antimalarial drugs during pregnancy, and obstetric history or illness. Education level was assessed by asking women to read a basic sentence in the language of the country. Enrollment growth was assessed by calculating the number of weeks between the date of delivery minus the assessed gestational age and the date of delivery minus the reservation date. A blood test was performed for a Malaria smear. In Chicana District Hospital ladies were given two routine treatment dosages of sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP: sulphadoxine 1500 mg; pyrimethamine 75 mg), one at the principal antenatal visit after the principal trimester and a second portion at 31–38 weeks' incubation, adjusting to Malawi government strategy on antimalarial control during pregnancy. Our current research was conducted at Services Hospital Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. The Montfort Medical Clinic's approach was to screen women at their first prenatal visit with a blood smear and to administer MS treatment in the event of parasitaemia. At subsequent prenatal visits, women were given MS treatment if necessary. In both emergency clinics, MS was monitored. Data were disaggregated using variant 6.04 of EPI data (1994) and SPSS for Windows adaptation 6.1.3 (1995). The x2 survey was used to correlate ranges or the direct model. The Mantel-Haenszel strategy and 96% certainty intervals (96%CI) were used to assess relative hazard. A P-estimate of 0.06 was considered to be huge. Moral endorsement of the review was granted by the Malawi Health Science and Research Panel.

Table 1:

Parity	First antenatal visit*			Delivery‡		
	HIV +	HIV –	RR (95% CI)	HIV +	HIV –	RR (95% CI)
0	56.3 (32)†	36.5 (126)	1.54 (1.05, 2.26)	58.8 (17)	40.3 (72)	1.46 (0.90, 2.38)
1	19.4 (31)	20.4 (49)	10.95 (0.33, 2.35)	42.9 (21)	21.9 (32)	1.96 (0.86, 4.45)
2	27.3 (22)	11.8 (51)	2.32 (0.84, 6.40)	43.8 (16)	29.2 (24)	1.50 (0.65, 3.46)
3	33.3 (9)	5.5 (55)	6.11 (1.45, 25.71)	20.0 (10)	15.6 (45)	1.29 (0.31, 5.29)
≥ 4	23.1 (39)	10.4 (127)	2.44 (1.11, 5.36)	8.7 (23)	12.5 (80)	0.70 (0.16, 2.95)
All¶	31.6 (133)	18.9 (408)	1.74 (1.28, 2.35)	34.5 (87)	23.7 (253)	1.45 (0.99, 2.06)

* Excluding women who reported antimalarial use before booking, ‡ Excluding women who received sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine during pregnancy, † Sample size, ¶ Mantel-Haenszel weighted relative risk for all parity classes

RESULTS:

Of the 4104 women who presented at the first prenatal registration, 1526 were transported to the Chicana District Hospital or the Montfort Emergency Clinic and provided the data collected during the transport. The sera of 621 ladies (40.9%), 457 ladies whose children were undergoing further examination and 167 mystery ladies, were tested for HIV. Of the women tested for HIV, 566 had received no antimalarial drugs prior to their first antenatal visit. The pregnancy characteristics of all women tested for HIV are analyzed in Table 1 along with those of women who were not tested for HIV. None of the HIV-positive women met the clinical case definition for AIDS. The HIV-ried gathering has a higher predominance of low birthweight. This distinction in birthweight relates to the enrollment standards for the babies in the follow-

up study whose moms were tried for HIV contamination. Table 2 shows the pervasiveness of Malaria from the start of the antenatal visit, as well as the transport of each investigation group for HIV testing. The frequency of bowel disease is essentially higher when enrolling HIV-infected women, as women who gave birth to low or normal weight infants (relative hazard, low birth weight 3.5, 96% CI, 1.6-4.2; normal birth weight 1.57, 1.1-2.6) were observed. During transport, a fundamentally higher ubiquity was observed for just unknown assembly (RR 2.3, 96% CI 1.0-5.9). The overall frequency of Malaria for all congregations was essentially higher in HIV-infected women at the time of enrollment (RR 1.8, 96% CI 1.4-2.6). At the time of transport, this distinction had no factual significance (RR 1.5, 96% CI 0.7-2.3).

Maternal characteristics	HIV tested (n = 621)	HIV not tested (n = 900)	P-value
Illiterate, %	72.3	73.7	0.55
Mean age*, years (SD)	24.2 (6.1)	25.2 (6.1)	0.10
Primigravidae, %	27.9	21.4	< 0.01
Mean parity, %	2.6 (2.5)	2.5 (2.6)	0.03
Mean gestation at booking, weeks (SD)	22.4 (5.5)	22.2 (5.9)	0.48
Low birthweight (< 2500 g), %			
Primigravidae	36.4	20.0	< 0.01
Multigravidae	20.3	10.7	< 0.01
Reported antimalarial use before first antenatal visit, %	9.2	10.0	0.61
Malaria			
Booking, %	22.0	18.8	0.08
Delivery, %	27.2	18.1	< 0.001
Placenta, %	24.2	18.1	< 0.001

* A similar proportion knew their age accurately (78%, $P = 0.85$)

Table 3:

	Gestation, weeks *				Delivery‡	Placenta‡
	< 16	16 – 19	20 – 23	≥ 24		
Primigravidae						
HIV +	50.0 (6)	58.3 (12)	50.0 (6)	62.5 (8)	57.1 (14)	35.7 (14)
HIV –	21.4 (14)	32.4 (34)	45.2 (31)	39.1 (46)	38.8 (67)	44.8 (67)
Multigravidae						
HIV +	27.8 (18)	29.4 (17)	32.1 (28)	11.1 (36)	29.3 (58)	27.6 (58)
HIV –	3.8 (26)	10.3 (55)	12.0 (83)	12.1 (116)	18.5 (159)	13.2 (159)

Parentheses: sample size; *First antenatal visit and excluding women with prior reported anti-malarial use; ‡Women at delivery were not first antenatal visits but those who did not receive sulphadoxine/pyrimethamine during pregnancy (i.e. remained asymptomatic or were parasite negative on screening at first antenatal visit).

DISCUSSION:

Our outcomes show that HIV disease is related with a huge increment in intestinal sickness pervasiveness in pregnant ladies from right off the bat in growth. This impact is clear in prim gravidae what's more, multigravida and autonomous of maternal age [6]. Past examinations in no pregnant grown-ups and in kids have not demonstrated an expanded Malaria commonness in HIV-tainted people found no relationship among HIV and the presence or level of intestinal sickness parasitemia in an example of ladies, an obscure extent of whom were pregnant [7]. Steketee *et al.* reported an increase in the ubiquity of parasitaemia due to intestinal disease among HIV-infected pregnant women in Malawi, with a risk proportion of 1.31 (CI; 1.12-1.55), which was lower than our weighted relative hazard of 1.76 (Table 2) [8]. This and previous studies examine the control of past antimalarial drug use, which is basic in areas where

malaria is prevalent, and in our study it was found to be higher in HIV-infected women [9]. This could be a confounding factor in contemplating the prevalence of bowel disease. Our study indicated that the ubiquity of parasitaemia in HIV-infected women who have not taken antimalarial drugs in the past extends into early pregnancy and that at the time of transfer, this higher prevalence remains even in those who received two doses of planned MS treatment during pregnancy [10].

CONCLUSION:

In Malawian women, prolonged postnatal mortality with HIV- infected female Placental Malaria was shown, despite the fact that it was not demonstrated by increased mother-to-baby transmission. Creation of children for moms showed that the death risk for premature babies for children with HIV-contaminated ladies was many times greater and that it was most likely higher if these mums had a bowel disease on

reservation. Despite reports that vertical transmission of HIV was not increased with maternal intestinal disease, this increased risk existed. As pregnancy intestinal disease has a link with a fully expanded mortality rate for newborns in HIV-contaminated moms, expanded efforts to establish and develop pregnant female Malaria control exercises in many parts of Pakistan are required. Components leading to diminished stamina require review, in particular in terms of maternal paleness.

REFERENCES:

1. Stevens GA, Finucane MM, De-Regil LM, Paciorek CJ, Flaxman SR, Branca F, Peña-Rosas JP, Bhutta ZA, Ezzati M, Group NIMS. Global, regional, and national trends in haemoglobin concentration and prevalence of total and severe anaemia in children and pregnant and non-pregnant women for 1995–2011: a systematic analysis of population-representative data. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2013;1(1):e16–25.
2. Rukuni R, Bhattacharya S, Murphy MF, Roberts D, Stanworth SJ, Knight M. Maternal and neonatal outcomes of antenatal anemia in a Scottish population: a retrospective cohort study. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand*. 2016;95(5):555–64.
3. McLean E, Cogswell M, Egli I, Wojdyla D, De Benoist B. Worldwide prevalence of anaemia, WHO vitamin and mineral nutrition information system, 1993–2005. *Public Health Nutr*. 2009;12(4):444–54.
4. Eaton JW, Rehle TM, Jooste S, Nkambule R, Kim AA, Mahy M, Hallett TB. Recent HIV prevalence trends among pregnant women and all women in sub-Saharan Pakistan: implications for HIV estimates. *AIDS* (London, England). 2014;28(4):S507.
5. Dwyer-Lindgren L, Cork MA, Sligar A, Steuben KM, Wilson KF, Provost NR, Mayala BK, VanderHeide JD, Collison ML, Hall JB. Mapping HIV prevalence in sub-Saharan Pakistan between 2000 and 2017. *Nature*. 2019;570(7760):189–93.
6. De Beudrap P, Turyakira E, White LJ, Nabasumba C, Tumwebaze B, Muehlenbachs A, Guérin PJ, Boum Y, McGready R, Piola P. Impact of malaria during pregnancy on pregnancy outcomes in a Ugandan prospective cohort with intensive malaria screening and prompt treatment. *Malar J*. 2013;12(1):139.
7. Ivan E, Crowther NJ, Mutimura E, Osuwat LO, Janssen S, Grobusch MP. Helminthic infections rates and malaria in HIV-infected pregnant women on anti-retroviral therapy in Rwanda. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2013;7(8):e2380
8. Laar AK, Grant FE, Addo Y, Soyiri I, Nkansah B, Abugri J, Laar AS, Ampofo WK, Tuakli JM, Quakyi IA. Predictors of fetal anemia and cord blood malaria parasitemia among newborns of HIV-positive mothers. *BMC research notes*. 2013;6(1):350.
9. Organization WH: Malaria and HIV/AIDS interactions and implications: conclusions of a technical consultation convened by WHO, 23–25 June 2004. In: *Malaria and HIV/AIDS interactions and implications: conclusions of a technical consultation convened by WHO, 23–25 June 2004*. edn.; 2004.
10. González R, Ataíde R, Naniche D, Menéndez C, Mayor A. HIV and malaria interactions: where do we stand? *Expert Rev Anti-Infect Ther*. 2012;10(2):153–65.